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Perceptions about Social Responsible Investing among Academic Staff: Evidence from the University of Cape Coast, Ghana

Daniel Agyapong^{1*} and Matilda Ewusi¹

¹Department of Marketing and Supply Chain Management, University of Cape Coast, Ghana.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration between both authors. Author DA designed the study, performed the statistical analysis, wrote the protocol and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. Author ME managed the literature searches. Both authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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ABSTRACT

Aims: The study focused on the perceptions about social responsible investing (SRI) among academic staff. The target population for the study were staff of the University of Cape Coast.

Study Design: The study employed the cross-sectional survey research design.

Place and Duration of Study: The study took place between September 2016 and December, 2016 at the University of Cape Coast, Ghana. The data was collected from Academic Staff of the University.

Research Methodology: Three hundred and two (302) questionnaires were given out for data collection but in all, a total of two hundred and eighty-five (285) responses were received and were used for the study. Descriptive statistics such as frequencies, percentages, Structural Equation Modelling were used to analyse the responses gathered. The Smart PLS and SPSS software were employed in the processing of the data collected.

Results: The study revealed that the knowledge about SRI concept was relatively low these

*Corresponding author: E-mail: dagyapong@ucc.edu.gh, daniel.agyapong2008@gmail.com;

respondents. However, it was observed these respondents were not much familiar with the principle of SRI in making investment decisions.

Conclusion: It was evident that social responsible investing ideology is not well diffused even among the learned communities such as the university. This can be attributed to the inadequate research on this subject matter by the research community, especially those from Ghana. It is, therefore, necessary that attention be turned to this critical area of research. For corporate bodies, it is an area where firms can obtain a competitive advantage, by reviewing their policies to incorporate such responsible behaviour.

Keywords: Social responsible investing; perception; academic staff.

1. INTRODUCTION

Social Responsible Investing (SRI) appears to be an increasingly important component of financial markets in a number of countries. In the United States, for example, it was estimated that more than 11% of all equity and fund holdings were in Social Investment Forum (SIF) funds [1]. In the United Kingdom, 59% of the largest pension funds, representing 78% of all pension assets, had incorporated social issues into their investment decisions by 2000 and this number had grown significantly over the years [2,3]. In other countries, Ghana and South Africa, the SRI industry is at an earlier stage of development. However, in South Africa, this appears to be growing at a rapid pace. This form of investment is gaining an increasingly significant share of overall investments [4,5,6,7,8,9]. Currently, SRI has become common as ordinary investors realise the power they hold to influence companies for the better. As such, SRI is moving towards positive screening with investment in companies whose products and services have a sustainable effect on society and the environment. Furthermore, investors are realising that socially responsible investments can perform just as well as other types of investment.

In spite of the increasing realization of the power of investors to influence companies for the better service delivery, there is little evidence of the perception of investors about SRI among potential investors in Ghana. This pioneering work sought to fill the gap in literature by analysing the perception of potential investors, whether SRI is a criterion in making their investment decision. Among other things, the paper will look at the relationship between the main variables of the study (deferring, environmental, financial, governance and social factors). The choice of academics for the study was due to the perceived level of knowledge of academics on matters of environmental, social

and governance. Besides, the income levels of these academics make them potential investors. The rest of the paper is divided as follows; part 2, is devoted to the review of literature; part 3 for the methods and materials; part 4 is the results and discussion and part 5 for the conclusions.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Social responsible investing integrates social and environmental issues into the traditional investment decision process. This has emerged as a new concept in investment due to the growing concerns for corporate social responsibility [10]. This practice dates back many hundreds of years and was rooted in some religions. For many centuries, most religious investors whose traditions support peace and non-violence have actively avoided investing in enterprises that profit from products designed to harm fellow human beings. Many avoid the “sin” stocks, those companies in the alcohol, tobacco, and gaming industries [11]. The recent roots of social investing is traced through many civil liberty and civil rights campaigns of previous century. During that time, a series of social and environmental movements, from civil rights and women’s rights to the anti-war and anti-nuke movements, served to increase the awareness around issues of social responsibility [12]. These concerns also broadened to include management and labour issues.

Over the past years, the Bhopal, Chernobyl, and Exxon Valdez incidents, along with vast amounts of information on global warming, ozone depletion, and the concomitant risks to life on the planet, have brought the seriousness of environmental issues to the forefront of social investors’ minds. Having protested discrimination in South Africa, the apartheid system, investors also began to look more achingly at the employment practices of companies in the United States [13]. Most recently [14], issues of human

rights and safe working conditions in factories around the world producing goods for U.S. consumption have become rallying points for investors who expect both excellent financial performance and good social and environmental performance from the firms in which they invest.

Although social responsible investment is not a new subject, there is yet no known explanation as to what its definition really is. Over the years, academic literatures have referred to a broad genre of investment practices that integrated the consideration of environmental, social and governance (ESG) issues by a perplexing array of names. Some of the common names include socially responsible investment, ethical investment, sustainable investment and, more recently, responsible investment [15]. These different terms used to refer to this concept have resulted in a confusion regarding the exact meaning of this practice. For this study, SRI is defined as an investment practice that incorporates ESG issues and ethical issues into investment decisions.

The theory of planned behaviour (TPB) predicts one's intention to engage in a behaviour at a specific time and location. It postulates one's behaviour is driven by one's intentions that is a function of an attitude toward that behaviour, subjective norms, and perceived behavioural control. The decision to undertake social responsible investment is driven by one's attitude to engaging in such behaviour. That is, attitude is a predictor and trigger of human behaviour. Human behaviour is under the voluntary control of the individual. Therefore, potential investors have the power to control where (type of securities) and how to invest based on available information. In social responsible investment, investors' decisions are often based on the integrated social contract theory (managers' ethical decisions), and the signalling theory (firms' responsibility to engage in voluntary disclosure) [16].

According to [10], SRI which integrates social and environmental criteria into the traditional investment decision process, has emerged due to the growing concerns for corporate social responsibility. However, the definition of the concept still remains unresolved. In effect, several terminologies such as socially responsible investment, ethical investment, sustainable investment and, more recently, responsible investment have been used in

literature [17,18,19]. [20] found that in building their investment portfolio, such investors consider companies that make a contribution to society. In evaluating companies for investment, preference is given to firms that have outstanding employer-employee relations, companies that make and sell safe and useful products and demonstrate respect for human rights around the world [19,20,21]. [22] found evidence that provides support for the existence of direct and indirect effect of participation in a human right on investment. Furthermore, considerations by such investors are a company's position on issues of corporate governance, climate change and carbon emission, political contribution, gender discrimination, investment in gambling and weapons [23,24]. [25] also concluded that social and explicit cultural variables have a measurable effect on investment.

Literature documents mixed results on the issue of social responsible investment. Existing evidence differs from one country to country and sector by sector. However, it is found to have gained grounds in developed than developing countries. [10] posit that the concept is already prevalent in developed countries but still gaining momentum towards emerging markets. For instance, evidence from South Africa indicates that while investors appear to have a grasp of ESG issues, there was sparse evidence of actual mainstream investment decisions. What was missing especially, was how they integrate ESG issues into investment decision making. Therefore, the perception about SRI though low in South Africa, it is still growing. In the Spanish market, SRI has a low perception among investors, though there are a lot of SRI funds available. According to [26], in the Spanish SRI market, many investors are unaware that the returns on SRI are the same as with any other fund in the same category, given that the management approach is the identical. The absent of relevant SRI information means investors continuously, rely on existing financial information such as returns on assets, growth prospects and other market information in making investment decisions. For instance, a 2013 PricewaterhouseCoopers report [27] indicated that investors believe providing return on capital employed is crucial in their evaluation of a firm. Other studies that posit investors rely on accounting, and financial information includes [28,29]. [30] concludes that retail investors currently are most concerned with economic performance information, followed by governance, and then corporate social

responsibility information. [25] observed occupational and educational variables were the most important determinants when making investment decisions. Most of these investors were women in their late middle age, highly educated, with middle and higher incomes. Their findings show lack of awareness of SRI financial products on the market.

Several studies [31,32,33,34,35,36] referred to SRI as being “young,” against theory that seems to suggest SRI is an old practice. Besides, none of these studies had indicated the age of this “young SRI.” Moreover, with respect to age, some studies have indicated younger age among other things in determining stakeholders who are much more interested in SRI. According to [37], age, gender, level of education and income have been used to explain the behaviour of both social investors and conventional investors [34]. Results from previous studies [38] have found that social investors are often younger with higher level of education. Furthermore, social investors are normally females of younger age, more educated [39]; and are often much more concerned about the environmental than financial performance. [40] found that one’s CSR inclination varies with the level of education. However, [41] concludes that one’s CSR awareness depends less on the level of education. Meanwhile, previous studies [42] suggest the SRI market is in the hands of those with the most knowledge. This is a motivation for the current study that seeks to explore the extent of individual investor knowledge and information on social, ethical and environmental investment. SRI investors have a higher level of education and knowledge and consequently, have a higher interest investing in SRI funds. At the same time, a higher income may be too much of a generalisation since a high level of education does not automatically guarantee a higher income [43].

From the previous studies, the majority of SRI investors behaved just like other rational investors; preferring financial performance of their investments, although they are much more interested in social and environmental effect of their investments. Thus, one can conclude that SRI is not an act of charity or an attempt to ameliorate a guilty conscience [21,43,44,38]. From the reviewed literature, a hypothesised relationship between deferring, environmental, financial, governance and social factors was proposed.

3. METHODS AND MATERIALS

This study focuses on the staff, potential investors, who are deemed to be knowledgeable, in issues of CSR and SRI. The total population of the employees in the institution is 1,400 people. A sample of 302 staff was selected for the study based on the [45] Table. A scale format involves the use of a special rating scale that asks respondents to indicate the extent of agreement with a series of statements to a given subject [46].

The SRI concept is rooted in the CSR philosophy. It is based on three tenets – environmental, social and governance (ESG) indicators. The questionnaire was constructed with reference to the elements and issues in the literature. The issues in the questionnaires were based on what empirical studies and theory described under the issues of ESG factors. The study employed mainly primary data sourced using self-administered questionnaires with a rating scale.

3.1 Structural Equation Modelling

The study employed structural equation modelling (SEM) to examine effects among the variables. SEM considers the element between each latent constructs and observed indicators. SEM is a blend of two statistical methods of factor analysis and path analysis into one broad statistical method [47,48]. According to [47], SEM consists of two-parts 1) measurement of the part that relates the observed variable with latent variable through confirmatory factor analysis, and structural part 2) that establishes the relationship between the latent variables with regression simultaneously.

The software employed for data processing included the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (Version 21.0) for generating the descriptive statistics and Smart PLS (3.0) for the assessment of the reliability and validity of the measurement and the structural models. Partial Least Squares impact on the analysis model (i.e. structural inner model) that examines the association between latent variables. In order to deal with this, it is expected that individual average extracted variance (AVE) is bigger than the squared correlation amid the constructs originating from the measurement model. Based on this, the concluding model is obtained by dropping constructs with factor loadings of less than 0.5.

3.2 Measurement of Variables

3.2.1 Financial factors (FF)

Financial factors (FF) were measured using indicators of financial performance such as return on capital, potential for growth, price of security, dividend policy, annual report of the firm, track records of directors.

3.2.2 Non-financial factors (NF)

Non-financial factors (NF) were measured using constructs such as environmental, social, governance and deterring factors.

3.2.3 Environmental factors (EF)

The indicators used included environmental policies of the firm, environmental management systems, pollution control, extent of water pollution, hazardous and solid waste, recycling efforts, level of toxic chemicals produced by the firm, energy efficiency and organization's level of emissions.

3.2.4 Social factors (SF)

Included indicators such as respect for human rights, product safety, workplace with health and safety, working conditions of employees, treatment of customers, stakeholder relations, diversity of workforce, equal opportunities, labour relations and social solidarity.

3.2.5 Governance factors (GF)

Included indicators such as accounting quality, information transparency, audit quality, shareholder rights, board structure, board skills, independence directors, separation of chairmanship and chief executive officer (CEO) as well as independent leadership.

3.2.6 Deterring factors (DF)

Included indicators such as activities related to pornography, gambling-related activities, activities that abuse the environment, supporting abortion practices, activities that abuse human and labour rights, activities relating to tobacco and alcohol, lack of transparency in business practices, support for repressive or dictatorial regimes, activities related to armaments and animal testing.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study sought the opinions of respondents on the different aspects of investment as well as social investment. Appendix 1 provides the socio-demographics of respondents in the study.

4.1 Knowledge on Socially Responsible Investment

In spite of the increasing realisation of the power of investors to influence companies, results from the survey showed half of the respondents (50.2%) did not have an idea about social responsible investment. Meanwhile, 49.8% of the respondents confirmed that they had heard of social responsible investment.

The results have an implication for how these potential investors respond to corporate entities' conduct of business in this society. As a way to gain further insight into the dynamics of social responsible investments, the demographic background of respondents with respect to their response to the question of whether they have heard of social responsible investing was explored. From Table 1, the results from the analysis of the age of respondents indicate those who answered in the affirmative were more for age range 46-55 (27), 56-65 (13) and 66+ (1). This is compared with those who responded *No* to the question that was asked. Responses from the younger age group (18-24) had less people (7) out of (10); the 25-34 group had 63 out of 114 responding in the negative. Similar response was observed for the 35-45 group, where 48 out of 94 responded in the negative. This result suggests people in the older age brackets (35 years and above) tend to have an idea about social responsible investing that the younger generation.

From the results, (103) out of the total respondents fell within the GHS1000-GHS5000 income bracket, had not heard of social responsible investing. Unfortunately, these respondents have the potential to invest. The remaining 84 responded in the affirmative.

It was also observed that awareness level increased with the level of education. After the first degree level, it is observed that the number who responded in the affirmative increases, compared to those who said "No" to the question posed.

Table 1. Idea about social responsible investment

Have you heard of socially responsible investing?		Number	Percentage	
Response:	Yes	142	49.8	
	No	143	50.2	
		285	100%	
		Yes	No	Total
Sex	Male	96	98	194
	Female	45	46	91
		141	144	285
Age	18-24	3	7	10
	25-34	51	63	114
	35-45	46	48	94
	46-55	27	16	43
	56-65	13	10	23
	66+	1	0	1
		141	144	285
Income level	< 1000	1	1	2
	1000-5000	84	103	187
	5001-10000	50	34	84
	10001-15000	6	5	11
	15000+	0	1	1
		141	144	285
Education	Diploma (HND)	3	1	4
	First degree	22	43	65
	Second degree	72	72	144
	Third degree	44	28	72
		141	144	285

Source: field data, 2016

4.2 Financial Factors of Investment

Making investment decisions require the consideration of several factors that can potentially affect its outcome, including financial and non-financial indicators. From the six (6) indicators used to represent financial factors, *returns on capital* received the highest rating (4.58) in terms of the factors considered by these potential investors before investing. This implies many people, especially those who took part in the study, made their investment decisions largely influenced by expected returns. At the extreme end, the results imply these potential investors are not so much concerned with the track records of directors, as long as they receive returns on their monies invested in a business.

This is followed by firm's potential for growth (4.17), the price of the share (3.81); dividend policy (3.61), nature of the annual report of the firm (3.28) and track records of directors (3.20) in that order. The implication is that investors consider returns on capital invested as a priority for making investment decisions, but barely look at the track record of the directors of a firm

before investing. According to a 2013 PricewaterhouseCoopers report, investors believe providing return on capital employed is often a crucial part of their analysis of the company's performance and stewardship.

Table 2. Financial factors

Financial factors	Mean
Return on capital	4.58
Potential for growth	4.17
Price of security	3.81
Dividend policy	3.61
Annual report of the firm	3.28
Track records of directors	3.20

Source: Field data, 2016

4.3 Perception about Indicators for Making Investment Decisions

One of the issues investigated as part of this study was the perception of the respondents about the indicators to be considered in making investment decisions. Investors would include the ESG factors into their investment schemes while investing and these factors according to the

priority of the investor, are environmental policies of the firm, environmental management systems, their pollution control in the community and the hazardous and solid waste produced by the firm (see Table 3). The firm's level of emissions was their least priority, signalling their low level of environmental awareness and concern. This is because the level of carbon emissions or all emissions in general are not measured, therefore, these potential investors are not conscious of the possible danger of level of emissions produced by firms and its effect on the environment and health.

In the case of the social factors, investors prioritized respect for human rights, product safety, workplace health and safety, and working conditions of employees before investing. The social factor valued by most of these potential investors is respect for human rights. This is in line with the findings in [21,19] and [20] who opined that in evaluating companies for investment, preference is given to firms with outstanding employer-employee relations, companies that make and sell safe and useful products and demonstrate respect for human rights around the world.

Respondents prioritized the factors for governance factors (Table 4) as follows; accounting quality of the firm, information transparency, audit quality of the firm's accounts, shareholder rights and firm's board structure. The implication is that the nature of the people on the board; its size and composition are not a priority in considering to invest in companies by these potential investors. Their initial pre-occupation in investing in a company would be the accounting quality of the firm. This is followed by information transparency. This implies the companies must disclose to potential investors, as much as, possible critical information required in making investment decisions.

In addition to the governance issues, respondents were asked to indicate and rank some factors that could deter (a.k.a. the negative screening before investment) someone from investing in a company. From Table 4, it was observed investors indicated that their highest deterring factor is when they realize the firm supports or takes part in activities related to pornography, followed by firms that engage in gambling. In the respondents' view, they would refrain from investing in a company that

Table 3. Environmental and social factors

Environmental factors	Mean	Social factors	Mean
Environmental policies of the firm	5.98	Respect for human rights	7.00
Environmental management systems	5.91	Product safety	6.71
Pollution control	5.71	Workplace with health and safety	6.46
Extent of water pollution	5.62	Working conditions of employees	6.43
Hazardous and solid waste	5.56	Treatment of customers	6.37
Recycling efforts	5.45	Stakeholder relations	6.05
Level of toxic chemicals from the firm	5.29	Diversity of workforce	5.70
Energy efficiency	5.20	Equal opportunities	5.60
Organisation's level of emissions	5.20	Labour relations	5.47

Source: Field data, 2016

Table 4. Governance and deterring factors

Governance factors	Mean	Deterring factors	Mean
Accounting quality	6.14	Activities related to pornography	6.55
Information transparency	6.02	Gambling-related activities	6.52
Audit quality	5.87	Activities that abuse the environment	6.48
Shareholder rights	5.78	Abortion practices	6.40
Board structure	5.52	Activities that abuse & human and labour rights	6.40
Board skills	5.38	Activities relating to tobacco and alcohol	6.20
Independence directors	5.26	Lack of transparency in business practices	6.11
Separation of chairmanship and CEO	5.08	Support for repressive or dictatorial regimes	6.04
Independent leadership	4.91	Activities related to armaments	5.73
		Animal testing	5.07

Source: Field data, 2016

promotes or engages in such activities. This supports the social and the cultural views of the people in this society. Similar finding was also obtained in [25] who concluded that social and explicit cultural variables have a measurable effect on investment. The least of their consideration were companies that engage in animal testing.

4.4 Test of the Theoretical Model

There was the need to probe further into the relationship between the main variables of the study (DF, EF, FF, GF and SF). A hypothesised relationship between some of these variables and their constructs, based on theory, resulted in the model displayed in Fig. 1. Moreover, after the initial analysis, factors measuring a variable that loaded poorly were removed. Only the constructs that met the SEM criteria were maintained in the model. The output presents a test of the direction, strength and level of significance of the path coefficients (gammas).

4.4.1 Measurement model

As a requirement, the results from the SEM conform to various validity and reliability checks such as construct validity, which was assessed using the convergent and discriminant validity tests.

4.4.2 Convergent validity

Convergent Validity is the extent to which items measuring the same concept agree [49,48]. From Table 5, it was observed the factor loadings and composite reliabilities, all exceeded the 0.5 and 0.7 benchmark respectively, set by [50]. With composite reliability ranging from 0.721 to 0.806 and a minimum factor loading of 0.539, this was enough evidence of convergent validity.

4.4.3 Discriminant validity

Three tests for checking discriminant validity produced results that justify this criterion was met

Fig. 1. Test of the research model (PLS, n=285)

Fig. 1. Test of the research model (PLS, n=285)

Table 5. Construct reliability and validity

	Cronbach's Alpha	rho_A	Composite Reliability	AVE
DF	0.582	0.624	0.775	0.539
EF	0.580	0.597	0.779	0.542
FF	0.257	0.282	0.721	0.570
GF	0.640	0.663	0.806	0.583
SF	0.620	0.642	0.792	0.560

by the model. This includes the Fornell-Larcker Criterion (FLC), Cross Loadings (CLs) and Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT). The FLC showed the square root of the AVE of each construct is higher than its highest correlation with any other construct [51]. For CLs, it is observed from the Table 6 that an indicator's outer loadings on a construct is higher than all its cross loadings with other constructs. Finally, HTMT Ratio (as it is required) indicated values of 0.85 and below.

4.5 Structural Model

As indicated in theoretical model (Fig. 1) five relationships were tested using the path analysis presented in Table 7. In the first relationship, DF was seen to have a significant causal relationship with EF ($\beta = 0.285, \rho < 0.00$). This implies that as people consider DF in making the investment decisions, it results in much more consideration for EF as well. Alternatively if

people perceive a company to have less problems, DF, then they would focus less on EF in making investment decisions in such companies. This implies, companies ranked low on deterring issues are likely to rank low on environmental issues as well.

Furthermore, the results showed a significant relationship between DF and FF ($\beta = 0.221, \rho < 0.00$). This implies as the firm engages in environmentally friendly activities, it is favoured by investors as a suitable organisation to invest in, thus boosting their finance and financial performance. Similar observations were made for GF and FF ($\beta = 0.177, \rho < 0.00$); SF and FF ($\beta = 0.188, \rho < 0.00$). Also, the results show that EF, GF and SF significantly influenced FF. Thus, firms that work on their environmental, governance and social indicators can create positive image for the firm. Such image could positively impact on the firm's financial outcome or performance.

Table 6. Discriminant validity

Fornell-Larcker criterion					
	DF	EF	FF	GF	SF
DF	0.734				
EF	0.345	0.736			
FF	0.272	0.298	0.755		
GF	0.401	0.497	0.325	0.763	
SF	0.368	0.477	0.326	0.505	0.748
Cross loadings					
	DF	EF	FF	GF	SF
DF3	0.825	0.304	0.248	0.252	0.232
DF5	0.596	0.146	0.139	0.237	0.230
DF7	0.762	0.276	0.193	0.399	0.357
EF5	0.250	0.749	0.254	0.366	0.314
EF6	0.314	0.799	0.213	0.465	0.400
EF7	0.180	0.652	0.191	0.235	0.343
FF3	0.165	0.166	0.636	0.238	0.163
FF4	0.239	0.271	0.857	0.257	0.309
GF6	0.339	0.391	0.244	0.765	0.392
GF7	0.310	0.381	0.286	0.841	0.357
GF9	0.271	0.376	0.207	0.675	0.428
SF7	0.301	0.393	0.303	0.388	0.816
SF8	0.318	0.388	0.229	0.391	0.700
SF9	0.182	0.264	0.169	0.358	0.724
Heterotrait-Monotrait ratio (HTMT)					
	DF	EF	FF	GF	SF
DF					
EF	0.555				
FF	0.664	0.746			
GF	0.659	0.799	0.800		
SF	0.598	0.775	0.740	0.815	

Table 7. Results from the structural model

R ² : EF = 0.158; FF = 0.155; R ² Adjusted: EF = 0.164; FF = 0.146 Q ² : EF = 0.077; FF = 0.071				
	Coefficients	F-squared	T statistics	P values
DF -> EF	0.285	0.090	4.601	0.000
DF -> FF	0.132	0.016	2.090	0.037
FF -> EF	0.221	0.054	3.785	0.000
GF -> FF	0.177	0.026	2.887	0.004
SF -> FF	0.188	0.030	3.188	0.002

The structural model was evaluated for reliability using the path coefficient, the Q² and the Adjusted R². From the theoretical model, two dependent variables EF and FF were set up. The Adjusted R² for the two ($EF = 0.16$; $FF = 0.15$) showed several factors in each case are unaccounted for by the model. Meanwhile, the Adjusted R² though low suggests about 16% and 15% respectively of them are explained by only the independent variable that actually affects the dependent variable.

Meanwhile, as [52] suggests, R² is more likely to be small for such perception and human behaviour studies, because human behaviour is difficult to predict. In such cases, emphasis is laid on the statistical significance of the exogenous variables. Results from the Table 7 showed a statistically significant predictors ($\rho < 0.00$) between the endogenous and the exogenous variables, except for DF and FF ($\beta = 0.132$, $\rho < 0.05$). Furthermore, the predictive relevance of the dependent variables (Q²: $EF = .077$; $FF = .071$) are more than zero for each of the variables in Table 6. The Q² values above zero indicated that the values are well reconstructed and that the model has predictive relevance.

Among other issues the study documents, companies that ranked low on deterring factors would be ranked low of environmental factors. Furthermore, investors favour firms with better deterring records. Such firms, therefore, become the target for investment which ultimately impacts positively on such firm's financial performance. Moreover, governance indicators ranked high impacts positively on the finances of the firm. Firms with high ordered social indicators also experiences improved finances.

5. CONCLUSION

The results suggest more than 50% of the respondents had not heard about the concept of social responsible investing. Furthermore, more

than 50% of the males and females responded in the negative when they were asked if they had heard of this concept before. Also, the older generation (35 and above) had relatively more people responding in the affirmative than the younger generation.

On the elements considered before investment, return on investment was found to be of prior interest to the sample selected. Although the majority indicated they had not heard of the concept "social responsible investing," they were, however, conscious of its principles and ideals. This is reflected in the fact that they would consider a company's environmental policies, respect for human right and accounting quality before investing in it. These potential investors were not ready to invest in companies that engage in or support pornographic activities, gambling and their related activities.

Generally, it was evident that social responsible investing ideology is not well diffused even among the learned communities such as the university. This can be attributed to inadequate research on this subject matter by the research community. It is therefore, necessary that attention be turned to this critical area of research. For corporate bodies, it is an area where they can obtain a competitive advantage by reviewing their policies and incorporating such corporate responsible behaviours.

The results have implication for theory. Existing finance theories do not incorporate ESG issues in their prepositions. This study, therefore adds to any existing theories in setting the platform for analysing investors' decision to choose a firm based on its ESG ranking and score. For policymakers, the study highlights the importance of ESG to the investor, hence, the need to formulate, implement and enforce such policies. For practice, corporate entities need to highlight ESG practices, since it can attract investors.

COMPETING INTERESTS

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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APPENDIX

Appendix 1. Social demographics of respondents

Variable	Description	Number	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	285	194	68.1
	Female		91	31.9
Age (years)	18 – 24	285	10	3.5
	25 – 34		114	40.0
	35 – 45		94	33.0
	46 – 55		43	15.1
	56 – 65		23	8.1
	66 and above		1	0.3
Education	First degree	285	65	22.8
	Second degree		114	50.5
	Third degree		70	24.6
	Others		6	2.1
Income level	Ghc 1,000 – 5,000	285	187	65.6
	Ghc 5,001 – 10,000		84	29.5
	Ghc 10,001 – 15,000		11	3.9
	Others		3	1.1

Source: Field data, 2016

Appendix 2. Educational level and income level of respondents

Education	Income level			
	Ghc 1,000 - 5,000	Ghc 5,001 - 10,000	Ghc 10,001 - 15,000	Others
First Degree	56 (29.9%)	9 (10.7%)	0 (0%)	0
Second Degree	110 (58.8%)	33 (39.3%)	0 (0%)	1
Third Degree	20 (10.7%)	41 (48.8%)	8 (72.7%)	1
Others	1 (0.6%)	1 (1.2%)	3 (27.3%)	1
Total	187	84	11	3

Source: Field data, 2016

Appendix 2: Questionnaire

Demographics

1. Gender :
 - Male []
 - Female []
2. Age
 - 18-24 years []
 - 25 – 34 years []
 - 35 – 45 years []
 - 46 – 55 years []
 - 56 – 65 years []
 - 66 and above []
3. Education
 - First Degree []
 - Second degree []
 - Third degree []
 - Others (specify)

4. Income level
 Ghc 1,000 – 5,000 []
 Ghc 5,001- 10,000 []
 Ghc 10,001 – 15,000 []
 Others (specify)
5. Do you invest?
 Yes []
 No []
6. If no why? Tick one
 Lack of information on investment []
 Not enough funds []
 I am just not interested []
 Other (specify).....
7. What are the financial factors you would consider before making investment? Rank the following in order of importance. (1) Least important and 6 most important.

Factors	Rank 1-6
Return on capital	
Price of shares	
Potential for growth	
Dividend policy	
Annual report of the firm	
Track records of directors	

8. Have you heard of Socially Responsible Investment?
 Yes []
 No []
9. To what extent do you agree to the following regarding what organisations do to be socially responsible? 1 is least agreed and 7 is most agreed.

Statements	1	2	3	4	5	6	7
They must provide benefits for everyone involved							
They must develop relationships with employees and customers							
They must establish partnership with local communities							
They must obtain competitive advantage							
They must make more donations and charity							
They must be involved in corporate social responsible							

10. What are the environmental factors you would consider in making an investment decision? Rank them in order of importance. (1)- Least important and (9) – most important.

Environmental factors	Rank from 1-9
Organisation's level of carbon emissions	
Environmental policies of the firm	
Environmental management systems	
Level of toxic chemicals produced by the firm	
Extent of water pollution	
Pollution control	
Energy efficiency	
Hazardous and solid waste	
Recycling efforts	

11. What are the social factors you would consider in making an investment decision? Please rank them in order of importance. (1) - least important and (10) – most important.

Social factors	Rank from 1-10
Stakeholder relations	
Working conditions of employees	
Respect for human rights	
Diversity of workforce	
Workplace health and safety	
Product safety	
Treatment of customers	
Labour relations	
Equal opportunities	
Social solidarity	

12. What are the Governance factors you would consider in making an investment decision? Rank them in order of importance. (1)- Least important and (9) – most important.

Governance factors	Rank from 1-9
Board structure	
Independence of directors	
Independence of leadership	
Separation of Chairmanship and CEO	
Shareholder rights	
Accounting quality	
Audit quality	
Board skills	
Information transparency	

13. Overall, which of the following would you consider in making an investment decision? Rank them in order of importance. (1) – Least important and (4) – most important.

Investment factors	Rank from 1 – 4
Environmental factors	
Social factors	
Governance factors	
Financial factors	

14. Which financial product have you bought?

Christian community mutual fund	[]
Databank Ark fund	[]
Islamic investment fund	[]
Other (specify).....	

15. Why would you invest in an organisation?

High returns	[]
Security of investing in sustainable products	[]
Advice from institutional financial advisor	[]
Ethical or religious reasons	[]
Social pressure for more responsible behavior	[]
Other (specify)	

16. Why would you not invest in an organisation that considers social and environmental variables?

Low returns	[]
Doubts about relationship between ethics and returns	[]
Failure to publicise the existence of SR products	[]
Lack of support or endorsement by the state	[]
Charity and donation	[]
Other (specify)	

17. Which of the following will deter you from investing in an organisation? Rank from the most deterrent to least deterrent with 1 – 10. 1 for least deterred and 10 for most deterred.

Deterring factors	Rank from 1-10
Gambling-related activities	
Activities relating to tobacco and alcohol	
Activities that abuse the environment	
Activities related to pornography	
Abortion practices	
Animal testing	
Activities that abuse and human and labour rights	
Support for repressive or dictatorial regimes	
Lack of transparency in business practices	
Activities related to armaments	

18. Why would you choose a traditional investment over a Socially Responsible Investment?

Because it is

Safer

Similarly risky

Riskier

19. To what extent would environmental, social and governance factors influence your investment decisions?

Really influences

Influences

Does not influence

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